

Fluorinated Quinazolones. Part V : Synthesis of Some Fluorinated Quinazolone Derivatives

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Synthesis of fluorinated 2,3-dihydrothiazolo-(2,3-*b*)-quinazolin-5-ones(I), 4-arylthiazolido-[3,2-*a*]-quinazolin-1,5(4H)-diones(IV) and 5H-2,3-diphenyltetrazepino-[1,2,4,5][3,2-*b*]-9-fluoroquinazolin-11-one has been presented and the mechanism of transformation of 6-fluoro-2-ethylthio-3-phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolone(V) into 3-amino-6-fluoro-2-hydrazino-4(3H)-quinazolone(VI) has been discussed.

As diverse biological activities have been encountered in organic compounds having quinazolone ring system¹, it was thought worthwhile to incorporate some additional heterocyclic moieties in the quinazolone nucleus to study their effect on biological activities of the quinazolones. In continuation of our previous work in the field of fluorinated 2-alkyl-3-aryl-4(3H)-quinazolones and thioquinazolones²⁻⁵ as possible CNS drugs, a number of quinazolone derivatives have been prepared by incorporating dihydrothiazole, thiazolidone and triazepine nuclei in quinazolone ring system.

The preparation of fluorinated 2,3-dihydrothiazolo-(2,3-*b*)-quinazolin-5-ones(I) involves the condensation of 2-mercapto-4(3H)-quinazolones with ethylene dibromide⁶ as given below.

Fluorinated 4-arylthiazolido-[3,2-*a*]-quinazolin-1,5-diones(IV) were synthesised according to the

following scheme :

First, 3-aryl-2-mercapto-4(3H)-quinazolone(II) were prepared by refluxing appropriate anthranilic acid with appropriate arylisothiocyanate in ethanol according to the method of De⁷ and the resulting mercaptoquinazolones were converted into corresponding 2-arylquinazolin-4(3H)-one-2-mercaptoacetic acids(III) by treating with monochloroacetic acid following the method of Singh et al⁸. The resulting compounds (III) were cyclised to corresponding

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4-arylthiazolido-[3, 2-*a*]-quinazolon-1, 5-(4H)-diones (IV) by dissolving in NaOH solution and treating with sodium borohydride. The structures of compounds II, III and IV have been established from their correct analytical data. The IR spectra of compounds IIa-IIIh showed sharp and intense peaks in the region of 2610-2630 cm^{-1} (SH) and 1670-1690 cm^{-1} (C=O). In the IR spectra of compounds IIIa-IIIh broad peaks in the region of 3210-3320 cm^{-1} (OH), 1750-1760 cm^{-1} (C=O acid) and 1665-1680 cm^{-1} (C=O) and absence of ν SH vibration at 2610-2630 cm^{-1} have been observed. The IR spectra of compounds IVa-IVh showed absorption bands in the region of 1750-1760 cm^{-1} (ring fused γ -Lactam C=O) and 1670-1685 cm^{-1} (C=O) and absence of OH absorption peak.

5H-2,3-diphenyltetrazepino-[1, 2, 4, 5] [3, 2-*b*]-9-fluoroquinazolin-11-one(VII) was prepared from 6-fluoro-2-mercapto-3-phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolone as follows:

6-Fluoro-2-mercapto-3-phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolone on treatment with ethylbromide in presence of alcoholic sodium hydroxide afforded compound (V) which was, then converted into(VI) by refluxing with hydrazine hydrate (100%). 5H-2, 3-diphenyl-tetrazepino-[1, 4, 5] [2, 1-*b*]-9-fluoroquinazolin-11-one(VII) was subsequently obtained by treating VI with benzil. The structures of compounds V, VI and VII have been established from their correct analytical data. The IR spectra of V showed absorption band at 1675 cm^{-1} (C=O) and absence of ν SH vibration at 2610 cm^{-1} . The IR spectra of VI showed absorption bands at 3310 cm^{-1} , 3460 cm^{-1} (NH₂), 1680 cm^{-1} (C=O) and a slightly broad peaks at 1625 cm^{-1} (NH₂ and C=N). The IR spectra of VII showed absorption peaks at 3270 cm^{-1} (NH vibration) 1695 cm^{-1} (C=O) and 1625 cm^{-1} (conjugated C=N) and absence of NH₂ peak (3450-3300 cm^{-1}).

Mechanism: The reactions of quinazolones with amines occur with initial ring opening between 3 and 4 position and the nitrogen atom in 3-position of quinazolone nucleus is eliminated as ammonia⁹ and there are numerous analogies for this type of reactions in the literature¹⁰⁻¹³. On the basis of above observation, we propose the following mechanism for the transformation of 6-fluoro-2-ethylthio-3-phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolone(V) into 3-amino-6-fluoro-2-hydrazino-4(3H)-quinazolone(VI).

The cyclization of 3→6 should be facile, however, a prior exchange of 3→4 remains a distinct possibility.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. The IR absorption spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer.

6-Fluoro-2-mercapto-4(3H)-quinazolone: Ethylchloroformate (3.6 g) and potassium thiocyanate (2.8 g) was refluxed in ethanol solution (8 ml) for 1 hr when potassium chloride separated out. A solution of 3-fluoroanthranilic acid (4 g) in ethanol (10 ml) containing 0.1 ml HCl was added and the mixture further refluxed for 10 hr and cooled. The separated solid was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dissolved in dil. sodium hydroxide solution, treated with activated charcoal and filtered. Acidification of the filtrate with acetic acid afforded white precipitate of 6-fluoro-2-mercapto-4(3H)-quinazolone which was recrystallized from acetic acid as colourless crystals, m.p. 322°, yield 49.4%. Anal. Found : S, 16.03. Calcd. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{FN}_2\text{OS}$: S, 16.32%.

7-Fluoro-2-mercapto-4(3H)-quinazolone: It was prepared by a similar method from 4-fluoroanthranilic acid (8 g) ethylchloroformate (7.2 g) and potassium thiocyanate (5.6 g), m.p. 298-300°, yield 52.47%. Anal. Found : S, 16.19. Calcd. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{FN}_2\text{OS}$: S, 16.32%.

2, 3-Dihydrothiazolo-(2, 3-*b*)-7-fluoroquinazolin-5-one(Ia): To a refluxing suspension of sodium

bicarbonate (1.36 g), ethylene dibromide (2 ml) in isopropanol (1.0 ml) was added a solution of 6-fluoro-2-mercapto-4(3H)-quinazolone (0.65 g) and sodium hydroxide (0.16 g) in 60% aqueous isopropanol (25 ml) over a period of 2 hr. The reaction mixture was refluxed for another 2 hr, filtered and the filtrate was evaporated to dryness. The solid obtained was triturated with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and residue was collected and recrystallized from ethanol affording Ia, m.p. 175°, yield, 43.21%. Anal. Found: N, 12.69. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_7FN_2OS$: N, 12.61%.

2, 3-Dihydrothiazolo-(2, 3-b)-8-fluoroquinazolin-5-one(Ib): It was prepared from sodium bicarbonate (2.72 g), ethylene dibromide (4 ml) isopropanol (200 ml), 7-fluoro-2-mercapto-4(3H)-quinazolone (1.30 g), sodium hydroxide (0.32 g) and 60% aqueous isopropanol (50 ml) as described in case of Ia, m.p. 204°, yield, 49.38%. Anal. Found: C, 53.89; H, 3.05; N, 12.62. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_7FN_2OS$: C, 54.04; H, 3.15; N, 12.61%.

6-Fluoro-2-mercapto-3-phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolone (IIa): A mixture of 3-fluoroanthranilic acid (3.10 g) and phenylisothiocyanate (2.70 g) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 hr on steam bath. The reaction mixture was cooled and the separated solid was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water and recrystallized from acetic acid giving fine crystals of IIa, m.p. 328-9°, yield, 64.3%. Anal. Found: S, 11.34; Calcd. for $C_{14}H_9FN_2OS$: S, 11.76%. Other compounds of this series (IIb-IIIh) were prepared similarly and are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—FLUORINATED 3-ARYL-2-MERCAPTO-4(3H)-QUINAZOLONES(II)

Sl. No.	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis %S	
				Found	Calcd.
IIb	351-8	66.47	$C_{15}H_{11}FN_2OS$	10.97	11.18
IIc	331-2	63.82	$C_{14}H_9F_2N_2OS$	11.00	11.03
IIId	315	74.53	$C_{14}H_9BrFN_2OS$	8.99	9.11
IIe	232-8	57.34	$C_{15}H_9F_4N_2OS$	9.32	9.41
IIf	345	70.00	$C_{14}H_9FN_2OS$	11.41	11.76
IIg	191	67.34	$C_{15}H_{11}FN_2OS$	11.20	11.18
IIh	267	61.81	$C_{14}H_9BrFN_2OS$	9.12	9.11

6-Fluoro-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one-2-mercaptoacetic acid (IIIa): To a solution of IIa (1.0 g) and sodium hydroxide (0.6 g), in water (4 ml) and DMF (7 ml), was added a solution of monochloroacetic acid (1.3 g), sodium carbonate (1.2 g), in DMF (4 ml), and water (5 ml). The resulting mixture was heated for 3 hr on steam bath with occasional shaking. The cooled reaction mixture was filtered, diluted with water (10 ml) and acidified with HCl to give a white precipitate of IIIa. The precipitated solid was filtered and recrystallized from acetic acid in fine needles, m.p. 190°, yield, 82.6%. Anal. Found: S, 9.47. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{11}FN_2O_2S$: S, 9.69%.

Other compounds of this series (IIIb-IIIh) were prepared similarly and are recorded in Table 2.

7-Fluoro-4-phenylthiazolido-3, 2-a-quinazolin-1, 5-(4H)-dione(IVa): To a solution of IIIa (1.0 g) in NaOH solution (10 ml) was added a solution of sodium borohydride (0.5 g) in water (5 ml). The resulting solution was allowed to stand at room temperature for 15 hr and then acidified with H_2SO_4 . The solid separated out was filtered, washed with water, sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water. The recrystallization of the solid from acetic acid resulted fine colourless crystals of IVa, m.p., 292°, yield, 74.4%. Anal. Found: C, 61.03; H, 3.43; N, 8.64. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{11}FN_2O_2S$: C, 61.14; H, 3.50; N, 8.91%.

Other members of this series were prepared similarly and are listed in Table 3.

6-Fluoro-2-ethylmercapto-3-phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolone(V): To a solution of 2-mercapto-3-phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolone (2.5 g) and sodium hydroxide (1.25 g) in 50% aqueous ethanol (25 ml), was added ethylbromide (1.3 g) and the resulting solution was stirred for 2 hr at room temperature. The reaction mixture was cooled and the separated solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from ethanol as colourless needles of V, m.p. 110°, yield, 73.50%. Anal. Found: S, 10.57, Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{15}FN_2OS$: S, 10.66%.

TABLE 2—FLUORINATED 3-ARYLQUINAZOLIN-4(3H)-ONE-2-MERCAPTOACETIC ACIDS(III)

Sl. No.	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis			Found/Calcd S
				C	H	N	
IIIb	340	81.7	$C_{17}H_{13}FN_2O_2S$	59.01	3.52	8.15	-
				59.80	3.77	8.18	
IIIc	190	80.3	$C_{16}H_{10}F_2N_2O_2S$	54.98	2.69	7.86	-
				55.17	2.87	8.04	
IIId	230	83.4	$C_{16}H_{10}BrFN_2O_2S$	46.68	2.32	6.69	-
				46.94	2.44	6.84	
IIIe	184	76.4	$C_{17}H_{10}F_4N_2O_2S$	51.17	2.43	7.00	-
				51.25	2.51	7.03	
IIIf	196	81.9	$C_{16}H_{11}FN_2O_2S$	57.92	3.17	8.13	-
				58.18	3.33	8.48	
IIIg	201	80.38	$C_{17}H_{13}FN_2O_2S$	-	-	-	9.12
IIIh	210	80.47	$C_{16}H_{10}BrFN_2O_2S$	-	-	-	9.30
				-	-	-	7.47
							7.81

TABLE 3—4-ARYLTHIAZOLIDO-(3, 2-a)-QUINAZOLIN-1, 5-DIONES (IV)

Sl. No.	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis Found/Calcd.		
				C	H	N
IVb	340-3	70.3	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ FN ₂ O ₂ S	62.01	3.82	8.31
				62.19	3.96	8.53
IVc	298	69.8	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ F ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	57.57	2.96	8.21
				57.83	3.01	8.43
IVd	214	71.3	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ BrFN ₂ O ₂ S	48.25	2.49	6.95
				48.85	2.54	7.12
IVe	289	72.4	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ F ₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	—	—	7.03
				—	—	7.32
IVf	312	68.8	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ FN ₂ O ₂ S	60.89	3.18	—
				61.41	3.50	—
IVg	289	71.3	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ FN ₂ O ₂ S	61.69	3.68	—
				62.19	3.96	—
IVh	203	72.3	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ BrFN ₂ O ₂ S	—	—	6.87
				—	—	7.12

3-Amino-6-fluoro-2-hydrazino-4(3H)-quinazolone(VI): A mixture of V(4 g) and hydrazine hydrate (30 ml, 100%) was refluxed for 14 hr and then cooled. The separated solid was filtered, washed several times with water and recrystallized from hot water to give VI, as fine needles, m.p. 220°, yield, 74.8%. Anal. Found : N, 33.33. Calcd. for C₈H₈FN₅O : N, 33.49%.

5H-2,3-Diphenyltetrazepino[1,2,4,5][3-2-b]-9-fluoro-quinazolin-11-one(VII): A solution of VI (1.05 g) and benzil (1.05 g) in xylene (50 ml) was refluxed for 20 hr with stirring. On cooling the reaction mixture, solid was separated out which was filtered, washed with benzene, followed by boiling water and recrystallized from aqueous pyridine as colourless needles of VII, m.p. 198-9°, yield, 63.02%. Anal.

Found : C, 68.72 ; H, 3.39 ; N, 18.01, Calcd for C₂₂H₁₄FN₅O : C, 68.92 ; H, 3.65 ; N, 18.27%.

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